

Evaluation of a novel Collision Probability approximation for local obstacle avoidance

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Abstract—In the domain of robotics, addressing motion uncertainty and incomplete environmental knowledge remains a persistent challenge for real-world applications.

This work presents a recently introduced approximation method for computing collision probability in continuous domains. We provide a concise overview of the theoretical foundations before introducing our proposed approximation technique. To demonstrate the potential of our approach, we conduct a comparative analysis against an established method within a trajectory optimization framework. The experiment results suggest that the proposed method offers promising performance in this context.

Index Terms—probability, optimization, robotics

I. INTRODUCTION

In the realm of robotics, the ability to navigate uncertain environments safely is crucial for real-world applications. As autonomous systems increasingly tackle complex tasks, from warehouse management to urban delivery, they must contend with dynamic obstacles and incomplete information.

A key aspect of safe navigation is the accurate estimation of collision probability along a robot’s planned path. Even with precise environmental maps, robots often lack complete knowledge about the location and movements of potential obstacles.

Existing approaches to tackle this problem have limitations. Chance-constrained methods [1]–[3], which rely on Boole’s inequality to sum probabilities along a path, tend to overestimate risk as discretization resolution increases. Monte Carlo methods [4], [5], while accurate, often prove computationally intensive and unsuitable for real-time applications: even when optimized [6], MC methods lack differentiability¹, limiting their use in gradient-based optimization frameworks. Methods based on the Lasserre hierarchy [7], [8] offer rigorous continuous-time risk estimation, but their high computational demands often limit practical application in real-time robotics scenarios.

This work addresses the challenge of estimating collision probability in continuous scenarios. We present a recently

introduced approximation method [9] that aims to balance accuracy and computational efficiency. Our approach considers the continuous nature of the robot’s path, avoiding the pitfalls of discrete approximations while remaining computationally tractable. To demonstrate the potential of our method, we compare it against an established chance-constrained approach using Boole’s inequality in a trajectory optimization framework. This comparison provides insights into the effectiveness of our approximation in realistic planning scenarios. This work aims to contribute to the ongoing efforts in improving risk assessment for autonomous systems operating in uncertain environments.

II. PROBABILITY OF COLLISION

Setting: Let a robot and an obstacle living in \mathbb{R}^2 be translationally uncertain disks $\mathbb{X}_R(R), \mathbb{X}_O(O) \subseteq \mathbb{R}^2$, i.e.

$$\mathbb{X}_{R/O} = X_{R/O} + x_{R/O} + w_{R/O}(\omega), \quad (1)$$

where $X_R, X_O \subseteq \mathbb{R}^2$ are disks of set radius, $x_R, x_O \in \mathbb{R}^2$ are the known translation vectors, $w_R, w_O : \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^2$ are independent zero-mean Gaussian random variables (RVs) and $R, O : \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^2$ are the RVs $\sim \mathcal{N}(x_{R/O}, \Sigma_{R/O})$ indicating the actual position of the objects’ barycenter.

Under these assumptions, the overlap condition is defined as

$$C(R, O) := \underbrace{w_d \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \Sigma_R + \Sigma_O)}_{(w_R - w_O)} \in \underbrace{S_d}_{(X_R \ominus X_O)} + \underbrace{d_{RO}}_{(x_R - x_O)}. \quad (2)$$

Now, let $x_R(s) : [0, 1] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^2$ be the continuous curve parametrizing the nominal trajectory of the robot with s denoting the normalized progress along it, then $\gamma_d : [0, 1] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^2$ parametrizes the distance d_{RO} as

$$\gamma_d(s) = x_R(s) - x_O. \quad (3)$$

Then the parametrized collision event (2) is

$$C_s := \{\omega \in \Omega | w_d(\omega, s) \in D_d(s)\}, \quad s \in [0, 1], \quad (4)$$

of which the probability is

$$P(C_s) = \int_{D_d(s)} \mathcal{N}(x | 0, \Sigma_d) dx, \quad (5)$$

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¹By being dependent on a batch of simulations.

where the set-function $D_d : [0, 1] \rightarrow \mathcal{R}^2$ is

$$D_d(s) = S_d + \gamma_d(s). \quad (6)$$

The event we are interested in computing the probability of is

$$C := \cup_{s \in [0,1]} C_s, \quad (7)$$

i.e. the probability of collision along $x_R(s)$.

Dependence Assumptions: Computing the probability $P(C)$ of (7) is untreatable and some simplification of the interdependence between various (4) is needed. We consider three simplifying assumptions

- (H1) $C_s \perp C_q, \forall s \neq q \in [0, 1]$
- (H2) • C_s has the Markov property
 - $P(C_s | \bar{C}_q) = P(w_{RO}(s) \in (D_d(s) \cap D_d^C(q))), \forall s > q \in [0, 1]$, where $(\cdot)^C$ denotes the set complement.
- (H3) $w_{RO}(\omega, s)$ is a stopped process $w_{RO}^{s_0}(\omega, s) := w_{RO}(\omega, \min(s_0, s)) = w_{RO}(\omega, 0)$.

In practice, (H1) states independence, (H2) assumes collisions can happen only in newly covered areas and (H3) considers uncertainty only in the initial configuration.

Probability under Assumptions: In the continuous scenario we are considering, (H1) does not lead to meaningful results [6], while the probabilities computed either under (H2) or (H3) can be reduced to integrals [9]. Consider the area swept by the combined disk S_d , with radius r , moving along the nominal trajectory. This subspace of \mathbb{R}^2 can be parametrized as

$$\Phi(s, \theta) = \begin{bmatrix} x_{R_x}(s) - \theta \frac{\partial \gamma_{dy}}{\partial s}(s) \\ x_{R_y}(s) + \theta \frac{\partial \gamma_{dx}}{\partial s}(s) \end{bmatrix}, \Phi_d(s, \theta) = \Phi(s, \theta) - x_O. \quad (8)$$

Then the collision probabilities under (H2) and (H3) are respectively

$$P_{H2}^a(C) = 1 - \exp \left(- \int_0^1 \int_{-r}^r \mathcal{N}(\Phi_d(s, t) | 0, \Sigma_d) \Gamma(s, t) dt ds \right), \quad (9)$$

and

$$P_{H3}^a(C) = \int_0^1 \int_{-r}^r \mathcal{N}(\Phi_d(s, t) | 0, \Sigma_d) \Gamma(s, t) ds dt, \quad (10)$$

where $\Gamma = |\det(\nabla \Phi_d)|$ and $\Sigma_d = \Sigma_R + \Sigma_O$.

III. RISK DENSITY BASED APPROXIMATION

It can be shown that $\partial_r P_{H2}^a|_{r=0} = \partial_r P_{H3}^a|_{r=0}$. We call the resulting functional ‘‘Risk Density’’, here detailed.

$$r_d(\gamma_d) = 2 \int_0^1 \mathcal{N}(\gamma_d(s) | 0, \Sigma_d) \left| \frac{\partial \gamma_d}{\partial s} \right| ds. \quad (11)$$

Using eq. (11), we approximate eq. (9) and eq. (10) as

$$P_a(C, r) \simeq r_d(\gamma_d)r. \quad (12)$$

For a set \mathbb{O} of multiple independently distributed obstacles (12) can be extended to

$$P_a(C) = \sum_{i \in \text{ind}(\mathbb{O})} r_{d_i}(\gamma_d) r_i = r_d^\mathbb{O}(\gamma_d)^\top \bar{r}, \quad (13)$$

where $r_d^\mathbb{O} : C^1(\mathbb{R}^2) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{|\mathbb{O}|}$ is the vector form of the functional (11) mapping a path to the vector of its risk densities with respect to all $O_i \in \mathbb{O}$, and $\bar{r} \in \mathbb{R}^{|\mathbb{O}|}$ is the vector of the combined radii of \mathbb{O} and the robot.

IV. EXPERIMENTS

A robot is to plan its trajectory $x_R(s)$ to reach a point hidden behind two ‘‘L’’ shaped corners, while keeping its probability of collision under a certain value.

The trajectory is parametrized as a Bezier curve of the 4th order $x_R(s, x_c) : [0, 1] \times \mathbb{R}^{2 \times 5} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^2$, of which we optimize the control points x_c to minimize the length of the curve. The ‘‘L’’s are decomposed in a collection \mathbb{O} of small disks, with $r_i = 0.1$, each distributed normally around their nominal position with identical covariance $\Sigma_i = \sigma \cdot I$. The same setting is investigated under different σ to analyze the effect of varying uncertainty on the optimization.

The optimization problem takes then the following form.

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{x_c} \int_0^1 \left| \frac{\partial x_R}{\partial s} \right| ds & \quad (14) \\ \text{s.t.} & \\ P_a(x_c) \leq c_{max}, & \\ x_R(0, x_c) = x_0, & \\ x_R(1, x_c) = x_F, & \end{aligned}$$

The constrained problem is implemented as unconstrained through the use of a logarithmic barrier function for the first constraint. In this case we have set $c_{max} = 0.2$. This formulation has been consequently discretized, with $N_d = 300$, and optimized using the `fminunc` function in MATLAB. To compare the efficacy of this method, both a Montecarlo simulation (MC) with $N_M = 10^4$ trials, and an approximation given by the right hand side of Boole’s lemma, are computed on the optimized paths.

$$P \left(\bigvee_{i \in \mathbb{I}} C_i \right) \leq \sum_{i \in \mathbb{I}} P(C_i). \quad (15)$$

We refer to this approximation as ‘‘Stagewise-approximation’’².

Results

Table I compares errors to MC simulation, with error $E_P = P_{est} - P_M$ and relative error $E_R = E_P/P_M$. Equation (13) has lower mean $|E_P|$ and $|E_R|$, performing ~ 2.3 times worse only in the first case, while 1.24–26 times better in all others, taking on average $\sim 0.3s$ for the optimization. Our method finds unfeasible solutions (red in table I), while eq. (15) mischaracterizes feasible paths (orange). Figure 1 illustrates eq. (13) tends to underestimate the values given by MC, while eq. (15) overestimates them. The behavior of optimized trajectories change with σ : low values closely avoid obstacles, intermediate values move further, high values yield straight

²The individual $P(C_i)$ s are approximated by the method detailed in [3]. The summation index set in eq. (15) is the cartesian product of the obstacle indexes and the discretization steps.

Fig. 1. Constrained optimization results. Left: Optimized trajectories by obstacle σ , shown by gradient, with a 3-std circle for reference. Right: Trajectory length and probability plots, including MC and Boole's lemma estimates.

σ	10^{-3}	$10^{-25/9}$	$10^{-23/9}$	$10^{-21/9}$	$10^{-19/9}$	$10^{-17/9}$	$10^{-15/9}$	$10^{-13/9}$	$10^{-11/9}$	10^{-1}	$\mathbb{E}[E_R]$
E_R [%] RD	-64.45	-36.39	-19.75	-11.24	-7.28	-4.85	-4.14	-4.86	-10.91	-18.51	16.54
E_R [%] SW	27.99	45.78	50.10	44.50	33.46	21.41	9.49	-3.03	160.37	152.77	64.48
σ	10^{-3}	$10^{-25/9}$	$10^{-23/9}$	$10^{-21/9}$	$10^{-19/9}$	$10^{-17/9}$	$10^{-15/9}$	$10^{-13/9}$	$10^{-11/9}$	10^{-1}	$\mathbb{E}[E_P]$
E_P [%] RD	-98.99	-97.55	-93.91	-86.12	-73.85	-56.74	-43.41	-36.91	-100.00	-100.00	80.78
E_P [%] SW	42.99	122.74	238.23	340.98	339.34	250.42	99.55	-23.02	1469.93	825.33	491.77

TABLE I

ERROR AND RELATIVE ERROR FOR EQ. (13)(RD) AND EQ. (15)(SW) W.R.T. MC. NEGATIVE NUMBERS INDICATE UNDERESTIMATION. RED INDICATES INFEASIBILITY, ORANGE MISCHARACTERIZATION. MEANS INCLUDE ALL VALUES, BOLD INDICATES MAXIMA IN ABSOLUTE VALUE.

paths. This relates to the peaking phenomenon discussed in [9]. Moreover, as σ increases, obstacle distributions widen, making circumvention comparable to straight paths in the eyes of the cost function, as illustrated in the second plot from right in Figure 1. Interestingly, our method accurately captures a significant behavior change occurring at $\sigma \simeq 0.033$, as shown in Figure 1. At this point, both the MC estimate and eq. (13) exhibit a downward trend, while eq. (15) demonstrates an opposite trend.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper has presented a recently introduced method to approximate the probability of collision in a continuous setting. The appropriate background is first presented along with the considered assumptions to then showcase the approximation. The experiments results showcase how the method can compete with other established approximations in the framework of trajectory optimization. We plan to improve this method by introducing a dynamical model of the robot and modeling both the propagation of uncertainty and observations. Moreover, work is being done to introduce attitude uncertainty in the formulation.

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